

THE STUDY AND IMPLEMENTATION OF THE SCIENTIFIC HERITAGE OF ABU ALI IBN SINO IN THE FIELD OF PHARMACY IN THE PERIOD OF AMIR TIMUR AND THE TIMURIDS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12749033>

Importance of the topic: It is one of the most important issues today to study the history of our country in depth, to be aware of the reforms carried out in each of its fields, especially to know to what extent the pharmaceutical direction of medicine developed during the 2nd renaissance period. How the field of pharmaceuticals developed during the period of Amir Timur and the Timurids, the extent to which the works of Abu Ali Ibn Sina were studied and applied to the life of society among a number of medical scientists in the course of development are relevant aspects of the topic.

The purpose of the research: to analyze and draw a conclusion to what extent Abu Ali Ibn Sina's works in the field of medicine were used in the field of medicine by Amir Timur and the Timurid period.

Method and methods: During the Sahibqiran era, every city had a hospital, where educated and experienced doctors worked. For example, in Samarkand there is a large hospital called "Dar ush-shifa", which was headed by the famous doctor of his time, Mir Sayyid Sharif Shirozi. This doctor was originally from Jurjan, he came to Samarkand at the invitation of Amir Temur and headed this hospital. Among the great doctors of these times, Khisamiddin Ibrahim Kirmani, Maulana Faizullah Tabrizi, and Mansur ibn Muhammad lived and worked. According to historical data, Maulana Faizullah Tabrizi used Ibn Sinon's book "Medical Laws" as a direct guide in medicine and was Amir Temur's personal physician.

Results: The library of Alisher Navai, the minister of the Timurid prince Husayn Baykara, contained books by Abu Ali ibn Sina, Abu Bakr al-Razi and other doctors. Navai gave a very high evaluation to Ibn Sina. He called it "a symbol of intelligence and thinking".

Conclusions: Based on the above information, we can conclude that during the 2nd Renaissance period, more precisely, we can see that Amir Temur and the Timurid era focused a lot of attention on the field of medicine. It is a joy to be among the main manuals of state medical workers. The fact that there are still many unsolved secrets regarding the above topic encourages us to conduct further research on this topic in the future.

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